

Fast-curing bio-based thermoset foams produced *via* the Michael 1,4-addition using fatty acid-based acetoacetate and acrylate

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ABSTRACT

This study introduces an approach for creating bio-based polymer foams exploiting the Michael reaction that could be utilized as thermal insulation. The thermoset foams were developed using a second-generation bio-based feedstock – tall oil. Tall oil is a by-product of wood pulping in paper manufacturing and mainly comprises unsaturated fatty acids like oleic and linoleic acid. The study explores the use of tall oil-based acetoacetates (Michael donor) combined with various acrylates (Michael acceptor), petrochemical-based (bisphenol-A ethoxylate diacrylate, trimethylolpropane triacrylate, pentaerythritol tetraacrylate), and bio-based (epoxidized soybean oil acrylate, epoxidized tall oil free fatty acids-based acrylate), to develop polymer foams that meet today's sustainability requirements. The developed polymer foams underwent extensive characterization. Matrix curing parameters were assessed by measuring changes in dielectric polarization during curing. Foaming parameters, including start and rise times, were precisely measured. The chemical composition of the foams was analysed using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. Their thermal, thermo-mechanical, and mechanical properties were evaluated through thermal gravimetric analysis, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and compression tests. Additionally, the content of closed-cell and the coefficient of thermal conductivity were determined, further characterizing the foams as potential thermal insulation materials. Foams from bio-based donors with petrochemical-based acceptors exhibited a range of enhanced properties. They not only achieved high glass transition temperatures (up to 85 °C by DSC and up to 108 °C by DMA) but also displayed a spectrum of mechanical strengths (compression strength ranging from moderate to as high as ~ 0.40 MPa) and good thermal isolation properties (thermal conductivity coefficient ~ 31 mW/(m·K)). Bio-based foams, derived from renewable resources, were characterized by properties fitting for flexible foam applications, such as low glass transition temperatures (down to -9.7 °C by DSC and down to 9.8 °C by DMA), reduced compression strength (approximately 0.011 MPa), and increased thermal conductivity (up to 46.7 mW/(m·K)), indicating their potential utility in applications where flexibility is a key requirement.

Abbreviations for polymer foam samples	Full name
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA	Foam from epoxidized tall oil fatty acids trimethylolpropane polyol acetoacetate and bisphenol-A ethoxylate diacrylate
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA	Foam from epoxidized tall oil fatty acids trimethylolpropane polyol acetoacetate and trimethylolpropane triacrylate

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Abbreviations for polymer foam samples	Full name
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA	Foam from epoxidized tall oil fatty acids trimethylolpropane polyol acetoacetate and pentaerythritol tetraacrylate

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(continued)

Abbreviations for polymer foam samples	Full name
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA	Foam from epoxidized tall oil fatty acids trimethylolpropane polyol acetoacetate and epoxidized soybean oil acrylate
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl	Foam from epoxidized tall oil fatty acids trimethylolpropane polyol acetoacetate and epoxidized tall oil fatty acids 1,4-butanediol polyol acrylate

Note: Abbreviations are based on previous research to maintain a consistent style with previous publications. This publication is one of four consecutive publications developed within the project “High bio-based content thermoset polymer foam development from plant origin oils (Bio-Mer)” (No. lzp-2020/1-0385) and is part of a thematically united series of scientific publications.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the pursuit of innovative polymer foam materials has garnered significant attention and research interest, driven by a growing recognition of their multifaceted applications across industries. Today, these materials have become indispensable in sectors such as construction (providing insulation) [1], packaging (offering lightweight and protective materials) [2], automotive (contributing to weight reduction and enhanced safety) [3–5], and increasingly relevant for defence applications [6]. Polymer foams, with their remarkable properties, including low density, exceptional strength-to-weight ratios, and outstanding insulation capabilities, enable these diverse applications [7–10]. However, the current global context underscores the urgency to explore sustainable alternatives, firmly rooted in bio-based materials, to address pressing challenges such as the depletion of fossil resources, environmental degradation, and climate change [11–13].

Conventional polymer foams, including the most widely used materials like polyurethane foams, have long been integral to various industries [5,14]. However, their extensive use has brought environmental challenges to the forefront. Notably, the production of polyurethane foams relies heavily on isocyanates, primarily derived from fossil resources [15,16], with no commercially viable renewable alternatives currently [17]. Michael’s reaction is an innovative approach that leverages bio-based resources to address the sustainability issues associated with traditional polymer foams [18].

The Michael 1,4-addition (also simply the Michael reaction) is a known chemical reaction utilized in various fields. However, in polymer chemistry, it is emerging as a novel approach [18–21]. One notable variant of Michael reaction involves the reaction between acetoacetates as the Michael donor and acrylates as the Michael acceptor [22–25]. Acetoacetates possess active methylene groups that serve as nucleophilic centres, readily engaging with the electron-poor double bond of acrylates in the presence of a catalyst. This reaction leads to forming a carbon–carbon (C–C) bond [22,26]. The versatility of the Michael reaction lies in its ability to facilitate the controlled synthesis of polymers with tailored properties, making it a promising strategy for the development of innovative polymer foam materials.

There are several publications that use different types of the Michael reactions for the development of foam materials. Coste et al. investigated soft foams using acrylated soybean oils and biobased amines in *aza*-Michael reactions [18]. Li et al. explored a one-step thiolene click chemistry and the Michael reaction to create a robust superhydrophobic/superoleophilic melamine foam [27]. Few publications describe the development of polymer foam materials using the carbon–carbon Michael reaction. Sonnenschein et al. delve into the utilization of Michael chemistry for producing a range of foams, including rigid, viscoelastic, and flexible elastomers [28]. The investigation employs acetoacetylated glycerol and petrochemical acrylates as raw materials. Despite the potential advantages of the Michael reaction approach, such

as producing foams with properties like polyurethanes, the choice of raw materials may not meet the contemporary requirements for a sustainable future. Naga et al. developed porous polymers through the Michael reactions between multifunctional acetoacetate and poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate [29]. The resulting reactions yield porous polymers with connected spheres, and the study highlights the ability to tailor the morphology and properties of these polymers by varying the polymerization conditions. However, the use of poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate, a petrochemical derivative, also raises sustainability concerns as the polymer industry aims to shift towards more renewable raw materials.

There are a few patents (EP3783048A1 [30]) and patent applications (US20080281006A1 [31], US20060069234A1 [32]) about the Michael foams. Each present different approaches to foam production, with various degrees of biodegradability and chemical origin. A common drawback is the absence of second-generation raw materials in their formulations, specifically second-generation free fatty acids. These patents collectively point towards an industry trend of seeking more sustainable materials but also highlight a gap in the availability of fully renewable and bio-based feedstocks, such as those derived from free fatty acids.

A key advantage of utilizing the Michael reaction in polymer chemistry is its ability to incorporate the Michael donor and the Michael acceptor from renewable bio-resources, such as tall oil — a second-generation raw material derived from the pulp and paper industry [33]. The use of tall oil fatty acids offer several advantages, such as reducing dependence on fossil resources. Also, tall oil fatty acids are not competing with food and feed production [34].

Acetoacetates can be synthesized from tall oil due to its rich content of unsaturated fatty acids [35]. The process involves several chemical steps, including epoxidation of double bonds and subsequent oxirane ring opening reaction with polyfunctional alcohols [36,37]. Hydroxyl group acetoacetylation is then achieved through transesterification with compounds like *tert*-butyl acetoacetate [38–40]. This versatile approach of selecting different alcohols provides the means to customize various characteristics, such as functionality, branching, molecular weight, and chemical composition. These adaptable properties enable the production of materials with a wide range of properties, making them suitable for diverse applications in polymer foam development.

Polyols offer remarkable versatility — the same polyols can also serve as a precursor for synthesizing polyfunctional acrylates. Pomilovskis et al. demonstrated this characteristic with tall oil-based polyols [33]. In this transformation, the hydroxyl group within polyols acts as a nucleophile, reacting with acryloyl chloride [41–43]. This process leads to the formation of polyfunctional acrylates that can be used as a Michael acceptor. Considering the above, it is possible to utilize the same second-generation bio-based raw material for synthesizing both Michael components. The utilization of the Michael 1,4-addition polymerization in foam development from second-generation free fatty acids presents an innovative pathway for producing sustainable materials with versatile applications.

In this study, we explored the potential of tall oil-based acetoacetates as key components in polymer foam development, combining them with a tall oil-based acrylate synthesized in our previous research [33]. Additionally, commercially available acrylates such as bisphenol-A ethoxylate diacrylate (BPAEDA), trimethylolpropane triacrylate (TMPTA), pentaerythritol tetraacrylate (PETA), and epoxidized soybean oil acrylate (ESOA) were used. 1,1,3,3-tetramethylguanidine (TMG) was used as a catalyst. The development of the foam also required the addition of additives as a surfactant (silicone surfactant with the trade name Niax Silicone L-6915) and blowing agent (low global warming potential hydrofluoroolefin based blowing agent with the trade name Opteon™ 1100) to form the cell structure.

Fossil-based commercially available acrylates were used to benchmark our bio-based polymers against conventional materials. This approach not only tests the compatibility of bio-based and fossil-based materials in existing applications but also aids in the gradual shift

towards more sustainable alternatives, aligning with current industrial practices and advancing sustainable material development. Our research delved into comparing these innovative materials' mechanical, thermo-mechanical, and thermal properties. Thermo-mechanical properties were evaluated using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and thermal properties were investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The chemical composition of the foams was analysed using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to gather information about the foam structure, and the closed-cell content was determined to gauge foam porosity. This publication elucidates the potential of utilizing tall oil-based components in the development of polymer foams with a wide range of applications and tailored properties based on the used monomers. We provide only an insight into the development of bio-based polymer foams using the Michael reaction as additives using chemicals suitable for the most popular closed-cell foam materials – rigid polyurethane foams [44].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

For bio-based foam development, acetoacetate from epoxidized tall oil fatty acid tris(hydroxymethyl)propane polyol (E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA) was synthesized according to previous research by Pomilovskis et al. [35]. E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA had an acid value below 5 mg KOH/g, a hydroxyl value of 36 mg KOH/g, moisture content of 0.03 %, and acetoacetate groups of 0.00484 mol/g. Acrylate from epoxidized tall oil fatty acid 1,4-butanediol polyol (E^{IR}TOFA_BD_Acryl) was synthesized according to previous research by Pomilovskis et al. [33]. E^{IR}TOFA_BD_Acryl had an acid value below 5 mg KOH/g, a hydroxyl value of 29 mg KOH/g, moisture content of 0.02 %, and acryl groups of 0.0034 mol/g. BPAEDA, TMPTA, PETA, and ESOA, Catalyst 1,1,3,3-tetramethylguanidine (TMG) were ordered from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Silicone surfactant with the trade name Nix Silicone L-6915 (L-6915) was ordered from Momentive Performance Materials Inc. (Hamburg, Germany). Blowing agent 1,1,1,4,4,4-hexafluorobut-2-ene with the trade name Opteon™ 1100 was ordered from Chemours (Dordrecht, The Netherlands).

2.2. System formulations

E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA as the Michael donor and different Michael acceptors, such as BPAEDA, TMPTA, PETA, ESOA, and E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_Acryl, were used to obtain foams. The molar ratio of acetoacetate groups to acrylic groups was 1:2. In the foam system, TMG (5 wt% of acetoacetate and acrylate total mass) was used as catalyst, L-6915 (1 wt% of acetoacetate and acrylate total mass) was used as a surfactant for improved shear stability. Opteon™ 1100 (20 wt% of acetoacetate and acrylate total mass), which has low vapour thermal conductivity and permeation rate, was used as a physical blowing agent. The Hauschild SpeedMixer DAC 250 SP (Hauschild GmbH & Co. KG,

Hamm, Germany) mixer was used to mix the components for around 10 s. The systems formulated are given in Table 1. Idealized structures of bio-based Michael components are shown in Fig. 1.

170 g of the total mass of acetoacetate and acrylate was used to make foam blocks to determine the coefficient of thermal conductivity and further test thermal, thermomechanical, and mechanical properties. The ratio between acetoacetate and acrylate groups was kept the same, i.e., 1:2, respectively. Also, catalyst, surfactant and blowing agent were kept at the same percentages of the total weight of acrylate and acetoacetate (TMG 5 wt%, L-6915 1 wt%, Opteon™ 1100 20 wt%).

The polymer matrix parameters were studied by the change of dielectric polarization. A total mass of 10 g of acetoacetate and acrylate without blowing agent and surfactant was used to cover the dielectric polarisation sensor.

2.3. Methods of analysis

The curing monitor device (CMD) (Messtechnik GmbH, Germany) sensor was used in the monitoring of materials' curing processes by detecting changes in dielectric polarization. CMD sensor is a component of the Foam Qualification System FOAMAT® 285 (Messtechnik GmbH, Germany), which is a device for measuring foam rising and curing.

The FOAMAT® 285, equipped with a sound centring blow tube (SCBT) (Messtechnik GmbH, Germany) specially designed for 60 ml cups, was also used to measure foaming parameters such as foaming start time, which is marked by the initiation of the expansion of the material due to the exothermic reaction between the components, rise time, which is the duration it takes for the foam to reach its maximum height, and foam rise height, which is the ultimate height the foam achieved at the end of its expansion. For all FOAMAT tests, the total mass of acrylate and acetoacetate was 10 g. Each measurement was repeated three times.

The Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS50 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was used for FT-IR spectroscopy analysis to determine the functional groups in the sample. Spectral data within the 4000 cm⁻¹ to 500 cm⁻¹ range were acquired via attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode using a diamond crystal. Each spectrum was the result of 32 accumulated scans at a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Bruker AVANCE-II spectrometer was used for ¹³C CP MAS NMR spectra. Spectra were recorded at 14.1 T magnetic field using home built double resonance magic-angle-spinning probe for 4 x 25 mm Si3N4 rotors. The spinning speed of the sample was set to 12.5 kHz. The spectra were recorded with standard cross polarization (CP) pulse sequence, where the duration of ramped polarization transfer pulse was 2 ms, CP was followed by the acquisition in the presence of proton decoupling by a strong frequency modulated rf field in proton channel. The relaxation delay between the excitations was 5 s.

The Mettler Toledo DSC 823e (Mettler Toledo, Switzerland) equipment was used for DSC to determine the glass transition temperatures (T_{g(DSC)}) of the polymer samples. The thermal procedure consisted of a controlled temperature program, where the samples were subjected to a heating sequence from -90 °C to 170 °C at a rate of 10 °C per minute.

Table 1
Systems for FOAMAT tests to characterise foam rise parameters.

Components	Foam system name				
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl
BPAEDA, g	7.13	–	–	–	–
TMPTA, g	–	4.89	–	–	–
PETA, g	–	–	4.60	–	–
ESOA, g	–	–	–	7.46	–
E ^{IR} TOFA_BD_Acryl, g	–	–	–	–	7.19
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA, g	2.87	5.11	5.40	2.54	2.81
TMG, g	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
L-6915, g	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Opteon™ 1100, g	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00

Fig. 1. Idealized structures of synthesised bio-based acetoacetate (E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA) and acrylate (E^{IR}TOFA_BD_Acryl), commercially available epoxidized soybean oil acrylate (ESOA) and commercially available petrochemical-based acrylates (BPAEDA, TMPTA, PETA).

This protocol was structured as a cyclic sequence of heating and cooling phases, and the $T_{g(DSC)}$ values were identified during the second heating cycle to prevent the effects of overlapping heat effects of curing chemical reactions [45].

The Mettler Toledo DMA/SDTA861e (Mettler Toledo, Switzerland) was used for the DMA to ascertain the glass transition temperatures (T_g (DMA)) of the materials. Samples, standardized to a diameter of 14.0 mm \pm 0.5 mm and height of 7.5 mm \pm 0.5 mm, underwent a thermal cycle comprising heating and cooling from -90 °C to 170 °C. The temperature ramp of 3 °C per minute and an initial preload force applied at 5 N were used, all within the compression oscillation mode with an oscillation frequency set at 1 s⁻¹.

The Discovery TGA equipment (TA instruments, USA) was used for TGA to measure changes in the weight of a material as a function of temperature under a nitrogen atmosphere. Samples, with a mass of 10.0 mg \pm 1.0 mg, were subjected to thermal scanning over a temperature spectrum of 30 °C to 700 °C, employing a consistent heating rate of 10 °C per minute. For the analysis and interpretation of the collected data, TRIOS software version 5.0.0.44608 was utilized. Each measurement was performed twice.

The FOX 200 (TA instruments, USA) was used for the determination of the thermal conductivity coefficient (λ) adhered to the ISO 8301:1991 standard protocol [46]. Tests were executed with an average temperature differential set at 10 °C, which was achieved by maintaining the cold plate at 0 °C and the hot plate at + 20 °C. The samples tested had dimensions of 200 mm \times 200 mm \times 30 mm. Each measurement was performed twice.

The AccuPyc II 1340 pycnometer (Micromeritics Instrument Corporation, USA) was used for the determination of closed content. The content of closed cells within the specimens was quantified in compliance with ISO 4590:2016 [47], using samples measuring 30 mm \times 30 mm \times 55 mm. Each measurement was performed twice.

The TESCAN TS 5136 MM SEM (Tescan Orsay Holding, Czech Republic) was used for SEM to characterize foam morphology. Foam samples, with a form factor of 1 mm \times 10 mm \times 2 mm and oriented to align with the foam's rise and its transverse axes, were sectioned from larger foam blocks. The surfaces of these samples were coated with gold using an Emitech K550X (Emitech Ltd, UK) sputter coater to make them conducive to SEM imaging. Vega TC software was employed for image analysis. For the foam varieties under study, the dimensions of cell length and width in both the rise and transverse directions were measured across a dataset of over 100 cells. From these measurements, the ratios defining cell shape anisotropy, denoted as R, were derived based on the comparative lengths and widths of the cells (length/width).

The Zwick/Roell Z100 (ZwickRoell, Germany) was used for compression tests to determine compressive properties, including strength and modulus, in orientations both parallel and perpendicular to the direction of foam rise in accordance with ISO 844:2021 [48] standard protocol. Cylindrical test specimens, each approximately 20 mm in diameter and height, were prepared using a crown drill bit on a drill press. For each foam type, six such specimens underwent analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Curing parameters of matrix and the rise parameters of developed foam

From the data shown in Fig. 2, it can be inferred that different polymer matrices exhibited varying degrees of dielectric polarization and reached different maximum temperatures during the curing process. In analysing the curing parameters of polymer matrices derived from tall oil trimethylolpropane acetoacetate combined with various acrylates, a clear relationship emerged between acrylate functionality and curing behaviour. Specifically, the curing process is expedited as acrylate functionality increases and a higher maximum temperature is achieved. For instance, the foam matrix formulated using the tetra-functional PETA matrix cured the fastest at 70.3 s and reached the highest temperature of 132.6 °C. The foam matrix formulated using the trifunctional TMPTA had a slightly prolonged curing time of 116.1 s and a temperature of 122. °C, while the difunctional BPAEDA exhibited intermediate curing parameters. Notably, when comparing commercially available petroleum-based acrylates to bio-based ones, the former tend to cure more rapidly at elevated temperatures. Specifically, the soybean oil-based ESOA and tall oil-based E^{IR}TOFA_BD_Acryl matrices had longer curing durations and achieved lower maximum temperatures. This underscores the influence of both acrylate origin and functionality on the curing parameters of these polymer matrices.

The behaviour of petrochemical-based acrylates in the curing process can be attributed to their molecular structure. These acrylates are typically smaller molecules, meaning the acrylic group content is larger. The high concentration of accessible acrylic groups facilitates a more rapid reaction, enhancing the curing process. In contrast, the bio-based acrylates derived from tall and soybean oil have a more branched and complex molecular structure. The slower rising profile can be attributed to the presence of longer alkyl chains in both bio-based acceptors. This structural characteristic influences the curing process, leading to a more gradual expansion of the foam. Also, this complexity introduces steric hindrance, which can interfere with the reaction process. The branched

Fig. 2. Developed polymer curing parameters: a) dielectric polarization curves and derivatives of dielectric polarization curves; b) temperature curves of the polymer matrix.

nature of these molecules makes the acrylic groups less accessible, slowing down the curing parameters. The curing times of all matrices and the maximum temperatures reached during curing are shown in Table 2.

The rise profiles of polymer foams show that foams from tall oil-based donors and petrochemical acceptors expand faster than those from tall oil-based donors and acceptors. As in the dielectric polarization measurements, this indicates that the origin of the monomer significantly affects also foam rise profile. It is influenced by factors such as molecular size and functionality, functional group accessibility, structural complexity, and alkyl chain length, as depicted in Fig. 3 and Table 3.

3.2. Chemical characterization of developed bio-based polymer

FT-IR spectra of the obtained polymer foams are given in Fig. 4.b. The absorption bands at 810 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the $=\text{CH}_2$ twisting vibrations, measured the acrylic group's presence. The acrylate-specific absorption bands, which are also typically seen around 1630 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} , are not analysable due to their overlap with the bands associated with the functional groups of the Michael donor. Observing a low intensity peak at 810 cm^{-1} within the spectra may indicate effective polymerization of the acrylic groups with acetoacetates, suggesting a high degree of conversion in the polymer formation process.

In solid state CP-MAS spectra (Fig. 4.a), signals of the characteristic groups can be observed. At 204 ppm, signals corresponding to a ketone present in the modified acetoacetate moiety is observed. It is present in all the analysed samples thus confirming successful addition reactions. Signal at $\sim 173\text{ ppm}$ corresponds to carboxylic group within the ester

Table 2

Curing times and the maximum temperatures reached during the polymer matrix curing process.

Polymer foam sample	Curing time, s	Max. temperature, °C
Bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$	243.8 ± 5.8
	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA}$	116.1 ± 1.2
	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$	70.3 ± 2.7
Bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA}$	291.8 ± 29.4
	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl}$	275.75 ± 30.6

Fig. 3. The rise curve and derivative of the rise curve of developed polymer foam samples.

Table 3

Characteristic of developed foams rise profile.

Polymer foam sample	Start time, s	Rise time, s
Bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$	42.9 ± 3.5
	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA}$	34.2 ± 2.8
	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$	20.5 ± 1.3
Bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA}$	57.9 ± 4.5
	$E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl}$	163.7 ± 8.1

moieties, while signals in the region from 160 to 110 ppm correspond to aromatic rings and double bonds. The signals of the latter are localized at $\sim 130\text{ ppm}$ and are visible in the sample where PETA and TMPTA, and, to a much smaller degree, $E^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_BD_Acryl}$ were used as Michael acceptors thus indicating incomplete reactions of the acrylate groups, most likely due to steric hindrance. In the spectral region from 80 to 60 ppm, signals of carbons of acylated or free alcohols and ethylene glycol

Fig. 4. Chemical structure analysis: a) Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy spectra of obtained polymer foams; b) ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectra of studied samples. The asterisks denote spinning sidebands.

chains are observed. At ~ 43 ppm, quaternary carbons from both reagents manifest. Intensive signals in the region from 35 to 20 ppm are produced by $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups of the aliphatic chains while signals at ~ 14 and ~ 7 ppm are characteristic of terminal $-\text{CH}_3$ groups in the acetoacetate moieties and TOFA chains.

3.3. Thermal and thermo-mechanical properties of polymer foam

Table 4 presents the glass transition temperatures (T_g) of developed polymer foam samples as determined by DSC and DMA and the cross-link density of a tall oil-based polymer matrix. DSC heating curves and DMA $\tan\delta$ are shown in Fig. 5. From DSC data for foams derived from a combination of bio-based donors and petrochemical-based acceptors, the $T_{g(\text{DSC})}$ values ranged from 16.8 °C for $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$ to 85.5 °C for $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$. Notably, the $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$ foam, which incorporated a tetra-functional acrylate, exhibited the highest $T_{g(\text{DSC})}$ because of a more cross-linked and rigid structure. In contrast, foams with bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor components displayed lower $T_{g(\text{DSC})}$ values, with $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA}$ and $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl}$ registering negative $T_{g(\text{DSC})}$ values of -1.9 °C and -9.7 °C, respectively. These differences highlight the influence of raw material sources (bio-based, petrochemical) and chemical structures (functionality, molecular weight) on the properties of the resulting polymer foams.

When comparing the T_g of polymer foam samples as determined by DSC and DMA, distinct variations were evident. $T_{g(\text{DMA})}$ values were consistently higher than those $T_{g(\text{DSC})}$. For instance, the $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$ sample exhibited a T_g of 16.8 °C in DSC, while DMA reported a notably higher value of 33.7 °C. Similarly, the $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$ foam formulated with the tetra-functional acrylate showed a T_g of 85.5 °C in DSC, but DMA detected a higher glass transition at 108.6 °C.

Table 4

Glass transition temperatures by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and cross-link density of tall oil-based polymer foams.

Polymer foam sample		$T_{g(\text{DSC})}$, °C	$T_{g(\text{DMA})}$, °C Loss modulus peak position	$\tan\delta$ max.	Matrix ν_e , mol/cm ³
Bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor	$\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$	16.8	24.3	33.7	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$ [49]
	$\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA}$	59.0	68.1	78.1	$2.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$ [49]
	$\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$	85.5	89.4	108.6	$3.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$ [49]
Bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor	$\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA}$	-1.9	9.3	26.5	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$ *
	$\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl}$	-9.7	-6.3	9.8	$0.71 \cdot 10^{-3}$ [33]

Notes: ν_e – Cross-link density (mol·cm⁻³) of the polymer matrix from previous research. ν_e is defined as the number of moles of elastically effective network chains per cubic centimetre of the sample (mol·cm⁻³).

* The calculation is shown in the supplementary materials.

Table 5 provides insights into the thermal degradation behaviour of developed polymer foams determined by TGA. The TGA curves and derivatives are shown in Fig. 6. The parameters include the onset temperature of degradation, the temperature at which maximum degradation occurs, and the temperatures corresponding to 5 %, 10 %, and 50 % weight loss. Additionally, the residual content at 675 °C is provided. The onset temperature of degradation provides insights into the initial thermal stability of the polymer foams. For foams derived from a combination of bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor, the functionality of the acrylate plays a pivotal role in determining the onset temperature. Although the temperatures were relatively similar, foam $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$ formulated with a tetra-functional acrylate exhibited the highest onset temperature of 374.6 °C, followed by foam $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA}$ formulated with the tri-functional acrylate, and $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$ with the difunctional acrylate. The increase in functionality of the acrylate and cross-link density of the polymer network results in enhanced thermal stability. This observation aligns with other studies found in the literature [50].

The residual content at 675 °C provided insight into the char-forming ability of the polymer foams. Among the partly petrochemical-based foams, $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA}$ left the highest residue of 4.65 %, followed by $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA}$ and $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA}$. This indicates that polymers obtained from higher functionality acrylates tend to form a more stable char structure during thermal degradation. The increased cross-linking density, attributed to higher functionality, contributes to a larger amount of solid residue.

$\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA}$ and $\text{E}^{\text{IR}}\text{TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl}$ have little bit lower onset temperatures of thermal decomposition than partly petrochemical foams, indicating reduced thermal stability likely due to their complex molecular structures. These values are slightly subdued compared to the more uniform and high-purity petrochemical-based foams. Foams derived from tall oil-based donor and acceptor also leave

Fig. 5. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) results: a) DSC analysis curves of developed polymer foam samples; b) DMA $\tan\delta$ curves of developed polymer foam samples.

Table 5
Thermogravimetric analysis characteristics of developed polymer foams.

Polymer foam sample		Onset, C	Max, C	T 5 % weight loss, C	T 50 % weight loss, C	Residue at 675 °C, %
Bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA	358.8 ± 0.4	418.9 ± 3.0	349.2 ± 0.8	413.0 ± 1.1	3.81 ± 0.02
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA	368.0 ± 0.2	421.1 ± 0.8	347.9 ± 0.4	420.0 ± 1.0	4.02 ± 0.14
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA	374.6 ± 0.3	427.7 ± 0.4	348.2 ± 0.5	425.0 ± 0.4	4.65 ± 0.12
Bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA	354.8 ± 0.7	391.8 ± 0.5	340.7 ± 0.1	399.9 ± 0.8	1.02 ± 0.05
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl	359.6 ± 0.3	392.0 ± 0.4	338.1 ± 0.2	400.4 ± 0.3	1.50 ± 0.07

Fig. 6. Thermogravimetric analysis weight loss and derivative curves of developed polymer foam samples.

less residue at 675 °C, highlighting a lower char-forming ability compared to partly petrochemical-based foams, which may relate to differences in cross-linking density.

3.4. Thermal insulation properties

Table 6 provides a comparative parameter of the thermal conductivity, density, and closed-cell content of foams, distinguishing between foams formulated using a bio-based donor with petrochemical-based

Table 6
The thermal conductivity, apparent density, and closed-cell content of developed foams.

Polymer foam sample		λ , mW/(m·K)	ρ , kg/m ³	V_{closed} , %
Bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA	38.8 ± 0.3	110.1 ± 1.4	7.7 ± 0.4
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA	32.3 ± 0.2	111.1 ± 0.13	68.7 ± 2.1
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA	30.7 ± 0.5	108.1 ± 0.3	72.4 ± 1.4
Bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA	46.7 ± 1.1	173.8 ± 1.6	32.7 ± 0.8
	E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl	44.5 ± 0.5	143.9 ± 10.2	45.3 ± 1.9

Notes: Rigid polyurethane foam: $\rho = 37.4 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $V_{\text{closed}} = 86 \%$, $\lambda = 25.5 \text{ mW/(m·K)}$. Data were taken from A. Sepevani et al. (sample F₀) [53].

Expanded polystyrene: $\rho = 28 \text{ kg/m}^3$; $\lambda = 33 \text{ kg/m}^3$, Data were taken from K. T. Yucel et al. [54].

acceptors and foams formulated from a bio-based acceptor and bio-based donor. The thermal conductivity (λ) of the foams showed a clear correlation with their composition. Notably, foams with petrochemical-based acceptors generally exhibited lower λ values, indicating better thermal insulation capabilities. One possible reason is the higher closed cell content (E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA, E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA). For instance, E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA, with a λ of 30.7 mW/(m·K), demonstrated the effectiveness of incorporating petrochemical components in enhancing thermal insulation. Conversely, foams from both bio-based Michael components exhibited

higher λ values (46.7 mW/(m·K)). On the other hand, the thermal insulation properties of the developed foams are well compared to other innovative insulation materials produced from bio-based and/or recycled feedstock. Liao et al. investigated cellulose-based multifunctional foam with a λ of 48.2 mW/(m·K), emphasizing good thermal insulation properties [51]. Pal et al. reported other insulation materials with good thermal conductivity, highlighting cork (40 mW/(m·K)), recycled glass (44 mW/(m·K)), recycled cotton (42 mW/(m·K)), and glass wool (40 mW/(m·K)) as effective alternatives making them suitable for various building applications [52].

As can be seen, λ depends on both the density and the closed-cell content. Foams with higher closed-cell content typically demonstrate better thermal insulation properties. In this context, the partly petrochemical-based foams generally exhibited higher closed-cell contents, as seen in E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA with a V_{closed} of 72.4 %. This suggests that the incorporation of petrochemical components may contribute to a more closed-cell structure. This effect is likely due to the smaller size and higher purity of petrochemical components, which promote uniform cell nucleation and stability, in contrast to bio-based components that, being mixtures of larger molecules, may lead to

Table 7

Scanning electron microscope images of the developed foams, taken both parallel and perpendicular to the direction of foaming.

Polymer foam sample	X perpendicular to the direction of foaming	Z parallel to the direction of foaming
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA		
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA		
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA		
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA		
E ^{IR} TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl		

more varied cell sizes and open structures. Higher density was observed in foams from both bio-based Michael components compared to semi-bio-based polymer foams. This difference in density can be attributed to the intrinsic material properties of both bio-based components, which might lead to a more compact, resulting in worse thermal insulation properties.

The SEM images provided in Table 7 show the structural characteristics of the developed thermoset foams. Across the images, there is a noticeable consistency in cell shape and distribution, which is important for the foam's performance in its intended application.

$E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA$ foam is marked by its large pores ($\sim 410 \mu m$) and high open-cell content. $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA$ foams presents a tighter, more uniform pore structure with visibly smaller pores ($\sim 260 \mu m$) than $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA$ foam. $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA$ foam shows the smallest pores with visible crack defects hinting at a brittle material. The high cross-link density of the $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA$ formulation delivers a cured polymer matrix while the foam is still expanding, which is the likely reason for the crack development during the foaming process. It is clearly visible that the functionality of the used monomer significantly influences the cell size of polymer foams. Monomers with higher functionality, like PETA ($f = 4$), tend to form highly cross-linked networks, leading to smaller cells ($\sim 150 \mu m$). In contrast, monomers with lower functionality, such as BPAEDA ($f = 2$), resulted in foam with larger cell sizes ($\sim 410 \mu m$), as there are fewer cross-linking points, allowing more significant expansion and resulting in a softer foam. TMPTA with intermediate functionality ($f = 3$) produced a medium cell size ($\sim 260 \mu m$). Average cell size in foams directly influences their thermal conductivity. It was observed that larger cells lead to higher λ , while smaller cells enhance the foam heat insulation properties.

The foams, especially $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA$ and foams from bio-based donor and bio-based acceptors, have an open-cell structure. The varying sizes and interconnected nature of the cells can be particularly effective for sound absorption. The irregularities in cell size and inter-connected porosity can help trap and dissipate sound waves at different frequencies, making the foam a good candidate for acoustic insulation [55]. In applications like padding or insulation where air circulation is beneficial, the open cells provide breathability, which can contribute to thermal comfort [56].

There were no significant morphological differences between the cuts parallel and perpendicular to the direction of foam growth. The pore structure, size, and distribution appeared consistent across both orientations, suggesting quite isotropic foam characteristics. Only sample $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl$ indicated possible pore size anisotropy ($R = 1.6$) in parallel cut to the direction of foam growth. The cell size anisotropy correlated with the compression strength of the developed foams, where it is similar regardless of the applied force axis in relation to the foaming direction. $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl$ foam had an average cell size of $360 \mu m$ in perpendicular to the direction of foaming, but in parallel to the direction of foaming the average width was $360 \mu m$, but average length was $560 \mu m$.

3.5. Mechanical properties of polymer foams

Table 8 presents the compression strength and modulus evaluated both parallel (Z) and perpendicular (X) to the direction of foam rise of developed polymer foams. The stress-strain curves of developed Michael polymer foams are given in Fig. 7. $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA$, $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA$, and $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA$ foams demonstrated varying degrees of compression strength. $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA$ foam, with compression strengths of 0.0073 MPa in the X direction and 0.0092 MPa in the Z direction, were less rigid and more flexible, potentially useful in applications where flexibility is a key requirement. In contrast, $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA$ and $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA$ foams exhibited much higher compression strengths (~ 0.27 MPa and ~ 0.40 MPa, respectively), indicating a more rigid structure. This allows for foams to be used as a thermal insulation material or other potential applications for civil engineering. This rigidity makes these materials suitable for applications where higher mechanical strength and load-bearing capability are essential.

Abolins et al. developed rigid polyurethane foams based on various formulations of epoxidized tall oil polyols with a λ of around 22 mW/(m·K) and compression strength of around 0.2 MPa, a value typical for materials used in civil engineering applications [57]. Although rigid polyurethane foams have slightly better thermal insulation capabilities and lower density, there is reason to believe that our obtained materials can compete with partly bio-based polyurethane foam materials in this area because the foam materials obtained in our study have significantly better compressive strength in the case of foam, reaching up to 0.4 MPa. The decrease of the apparent density could be achieved by the optimization of the foaming process, catalyst package and blowing agent content.

4. Conclusions

We believe this study provides the first valuable insights into the development of bio-based polymer foams using the Michael reaction. Foams were formulated from tall oil-based acrylate and tall oil-based acetoacetate, offering a promising pathway towards reducing reliance on non-renewable resources and mitigating environmental impact in the polymer industry.

Foams combining tall oil-based donors with petrochemical acceptors feature high glass transition temperatures, good thermal insulation, enhanced mechanical strength, and superior thermal stability up to $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. $E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA$ foams, exhibit the highest glass transition temperature and compression strength, along with the lowest thermal conductivity, making them good for high insulation and structural applications. Foams from tall oil-based both Michael components have lower glass transition temperatures, lower compression strength, and a little bit higher thermal conductivity compared to those incorporating a petrochemical-based acrylate. However, the thermal insulation properties of the developed foams are good compared to other innovative insulation materials produced from bio-based and/or recycled feedstock. Foams from tall oil-based both Michael components have a flexible nature, making them versatile for applications like packaging,

Table 8
The mechanical properties of developed foams.

	Polymer foam sample	X		Z	
		E, MPa	$\sigma_{10\%}$, MPa	E, MPa	$\sigma_{10\%}$, MPa
Bio-based donor and petrochemical-based acceptor	$E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BPAEDA$	0.041 ± 0.006	0.0073 ± 0.0003	0.079 ± 0.013	0.0092 ± 0.0007
	$E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_TMPTA$	7.6 ± 0.3	0.274 ± 0.007	5.1 ± 0.5	0.263 ± 0.011
	$E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_PETA$	9.7 ± 0.5	0.39 ± 0.02	7.6 ± 0.4	0.400 ± 0.010
Bio-based donor and bio-based acceptor	$E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_ESOA$	0.10 ± 0.02	0.0158 ± 0.0017	0.12 ± 0.02	0.0147 ± 0.0004
	$E^{IR}TOFA_TMP_AA_BD_Acryl$	0.12 ± 0.02	0.0111 ± 0.0016	0.09 ± 0.02	0.0074 ± 0.0005

Notes: Rigid polyurethane foam: compression strength 0.21 MPa, compression modulus 5.1 MPa. Data were taken from A. Septevani et al. (sample F_0) [53]. Expanded polystyrene: compression strength 0.18–0.26 MPa, compression modulus 1.8–3.1 MPa. Data were taken from K. T. Yucel et al. [54].

Fig. 7. Compression test curves of developed polymer foam: a) perpendicular (X) to the direction of foam rise of developed polymer foams; b) parallel (Z) to the direction of foam rise of developed polymer foams.

cushioning, automotive interiors, and certain construction uses where flexibility is beneficial.

The development of bio-based foams using the Michael components marks a significant step towards sustainable materials, thanks to their high renewable content. However, their higher thermal conductivity and density limit their use in lightweight, high-performance insulation applications. In contrast, partly petrochemical-based foams, offering superior insulation, fall short on environmental issues. This juxtaposition underscores the need for future research to enhance the properties of bio-based foams, exploring advanced blowing agents, surfactants, and tailored monomer functionality, which is crucial to achieving an optimal balance between today's sustainability and practical performance requirements.

Declaration of competing interest

No conflict of interest.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ralfs Pomilovskis: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Eliza Kaulina:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Arnis Abolins:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Inese Mierina:** Data curation. **Ivo Heinmaa:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Software, Visualization. **Vitalijs Rjabovs:** Data curation, Methodology, Software, Visualization. **Anda Fridrihsone:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Mikelis Kirpluks:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] D. Feldman, Polymeric foam materials for insulation in buildings, *Mater. Energy Effic. Therm. Conf. Build.* (2010) 257–273, <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845699277.2.257>.
- [2] M. Niaounakis, Foaming and Foamed Products, in: *Biopolym. Process. Prod.*, Elsevier Science, 2015; pp. 327–359. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-323-26698-7.00009-X.
- [3] A. Baroutaji, A. Arjunan, A. Niknejad, T. Tran, A.-G. Olabi, Application of Cellular material in crashworthiness applications: an overview, Elsevier Ltd. (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-803581-8.09268-7>.
- [4] M.Y. Lyu, T.G. Choi, Research trends in polymer materials for use in lightweight vehicles, *Int. J. Precis. Eng. Manuf.* 16 (2015) 213–220, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12541-015-0029-x>.
- [5] F.M. De Souza, Y. Desai, R.K. Gupta, Introduction to polymeric foams, *ACS Symp. Ser.* 1439 (2023) 1–23, <https://doi.org/10.1021/bk-2023-1439.ch001>.
- [6] S. Siengchin, A review on lightweight materials for defence applications: present and future developments, *Def. Technol.* 24 (2023) 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dt.2023.02.025>.
- [7] F.L. Jin, M. Zhao, M. Park, S.J. Park, Recent trends of foaming in polymer processing: a review, *Polymers (Basel)* 11 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11060953>.
- [8] G. Wu, P. Xie, H. Yang, K. Dang, Y. Xu, M. Sain, L.S. Turng, W. Yang, A review of thermoplastic polymer foams for functional applications, *J. Mater. Sci.* 56 (2021) 11579–11604, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-021-06034-6>.
- [9] L. Li, D. Xu, S. Bai, N. Chen, Q. Wang, Progress in preparation of high-performance and multi-functional polymer foams, *J. Polym. Sci.* (2023) 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pol.20230490>.
- [10] Z. Wang, C. Wang, Y. Gao, Z. Li, Y. Shang, H. Li, Porous thermal insulation polyurethane foam materials, *Polymers (Basel)* 15 (2023) 3818, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15183818>.
- [11] S.B. Murmu, Alternatives derived from renewable natural fibre to replace conventional polyurethane rigid foam insulation, *Clean. Eng. Technol.* 8 (2022) 100513, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2022.100513>.
- [12] A. Agrawal, R. Kaur, R.S. Walia, PU foam derived from renewable sources: perspective on properties enhancement: an overview, *Eur. Polym. J.* 95 (2017) 255–274, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2017.08.022>.
- [13] N. Singh, O.A. Ogunseitan, M.H. Wong, Y. Tang, Sustainable materials alternative to petrochemical plastics pollution: a review analysis, *Sustain. Horizons.* 2 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.horiz.2022.100016>.
- [14] S.A. Madbouly, Novel recycling processes for thermoset polyurethane foams, *Curr. Opin. Green Sustain. Chem.* 42 (2023) 100835, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100835>.
- [15] S. Sambhudevan, H. S. A. Reghunadhan, Polyurethane from Sustainable Routes, in: *Polyurethane Chem. Renew. Polyols Isocyanates*, Am. Chem. Soc., 2021; pp. 75–106. DOI: 10.1021/bk-2021-1380.ch004.
- [16] M. Wloch, K. Błażek, Isocyanate-Free Polyurethanes, in: 2021; pp. 107–166. DOI: 10.1021/bk-2021-1380.ch005.

- [17] J. Niesiobędzka, J. Datta, Challenges and recent advances in bio-based isocyanate production, *Green Chem.* 25 (2023) 2482–2504, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2gc04644j>.
- [18] G. Coste, C. Negrell, L. Averous, S. Caillol, Green synthesis of biobased soft foams by the Aza-Michael reaction, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 10 (2022) 8549–8558, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.2c01885>.
- [19] A.O. Konuray, F. Liendo, X. Fernández-Francos, A. Serra, M. Sangermano, X. Ramis, Sequential curing of thiol-acetoacetate-acrylate thermosets by latent Michael addition reactions, *Polymer (Guildf)* 113 (2017) 193–199, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2017.02.072>.
- [20] Q. Jiang, Y.L. Zhang, Y. Du, M. Tang, L. Jiang, W. Huang, H. Yang, X. Xue, B. Jiang, Preparation of hyperbranched polymers by oxo-Michael addition polymerization, *Polym. Chem.* 11 (2020) 1298–1306, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9py01686d>.
- [21] Z. Ma, Y. Zeng, X. He, S. Pan, Y. Wei, B. Wang, L. Tao, Introducing the aza-Michael addition reaction between acrylate and dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thione into polymer chemistry, *Polym. Chem.* 13 (2022) 6322–6327, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2PY01130A>.
- [22] S.R. Williams, K.M. Miller, T.E. Long, Michael addition reaction kinetics of acetoacetates and acrylates for the formation of polymeric networks, *Prog. React. Kinet. Mech.* 32 (2007) 165–194, <https://doi.org/10.3184/146867807X247730>.
- [23] M. Iwamura, Y. Gotoh, T. Hashimoto, R. Sakurai, Michael addition reactions of acetoacetates and malonates with acrylates in water under strongly alkaline conditions, *Tetrahedron Lett.* 46 (2005) 6275–6277, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tetlet.2005.07.045>.
- [24] A.O. Konuray, A. Ruiz, J.M. Morancho, J.M. Salla, X. Fernández-Francos, A. Serra, X. Ramis, Sequential dual curing by selective Michael addition and free radical polymerization of acetoacetate-acrylate-methacrylate mixtures, *Eur. Polym. J.* 98 (2018) 39–46, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2017.11.003>.
- [25] M. Gould, T. Hammond, S. Narayan-Sarathy, Radiation Curable Michael Addition Resins Having Built-In Photoinitiators, US20050261388A1, 2005.
- [26] B.D. Mather, K. Viswanathan, K.M. Miller, T.E. Long, Michael addition reactions in macromolecular design for emerging technologies, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 31 (2006) 487–531, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2006.03.001>.
- [27] M. Li, Y. Fang, C. Liu, M. Zhou, X. Miao, Y. Pei, Y. Yan, W. Xiao, H. Qiu, L. Wu, Facile generation of highly durable thiol-functionalized polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane based superhydrophobic melamine foam, *Front. Chem. Sci. Eng.* 16 (2022) 1247–1258, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11705-021-2124-0>.
- [28] M.F. Sonnenschein, J.B. Werness, K.A. Patankar, X. Jin, M.Z. Larive, From rigid and flexible foams to elastomers via Michael addition chemistry, *Polymer (Guildf)* 106 (2016) 128–139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2016.10.054>.
- [29] N. Naga, M. Satoh, T. Magara, K. Ahmed, T. Nakano, Synthesis of porous polymers by means of Michael addition reaction of multifunctional acetoacetate and poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate, *Eur. Polym. J.* 162 (2022) 110901, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2021.110901>.
- [30] D. Trumbo, N. Krogman, D. Nelson, A Method for Applying a Foam Composition Using Spray Foam Equipment, EP3783048A1, 2021.
- [31] J.O.L. Robert, L.K.-E. Michelle, O.F. Nassreen, One-Part Non-Toxic Spray Foam, US2008281006A1, 2008.
- [32] T.F. Kauffman, D.W. Whitman, M.J. Zajackowski, V. David Elmer, Biomass Based Michael Addition Compositions, US 2006/0069234 A1, 2006.
- [33] R. Pomilovskis, E. Kaulina, I. Mierina, A. Abolins, O. Kockova, A. Fridrihsone, M. Kirpluks, Wood pulp industry by-product valorization for acrylate synthesis and bio-based polymer development via Michael addition reaction, *J. Bioresour. Bioprod.* 8 (2023) 265–279, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobab.2023.06.001>.
- [34] L. Vevere, A. Fridrihsone, M. Kirpluks, U. Cabulis, A review of wood biomass-based fatty acids and rosin acids use in polymeric materials, *Polymers (Basel)* 12 (2020) 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12112706>.
- [35] R. Pomilovskis, I. Mierina, H. Beneš, O. Trhlíková, A. Abolins, A. Fridrihsone, M. Kirpluks, The synthesis of bio-based Michael donors from tall oil fatty acids for polymer development, *Polymers (Basel)* 14 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14194107>.
- [36] M. Kirpluks, R. Pomilovskis, E. Vanags, A. Abolins, I. Mierina, A. Fridrihsone, Influence of different synthesis conditions on the chemo-enzymatic epoxidation of tall oil fatty acids, *Process Biochem.* 122 (2022) 38–49, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2022.08.024>.
- [37] A. Saputra, P. Satwikantya, F. Puspita, M.W. Sya'bani, M.F. Agustian, W. Pambudi, Synthesis of epoxy oil from Waste Cooking Oil (WCO) using acetic acid and amberlite resin IR-120 as catalyst, *Eng. Appl. Sci. Res.* 50 (2023) 335–342. DOI: 10.14456/easr.2023.36.
- [38] M.C. Hennessy, T.P. O'Sullivan, Recent advances in the transesterification of β -keto esters, *RSC Adv.* 11 (2021) 22859–22920, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ra03513d>.
- [39] H. Zuo, Z. Cao, J. Shu, D. Xu, J. Zhong, J. Zhao, T. Wang, Y. Chen, F. Gao, L. Shen, Effect of structure on the properties of ambient-cured coating films prepared via a Michael addition reaction based on an acetoacetate-modified castor oil prepared by thiol-ene coupling, *Prog. Org. Coatings.* 135 (2019) 27–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2019.05.032>.
- [40] R.K. Pandey, P. Kumar, A facile procedure for transesterification of β -keto esters promoted by ceria-yttria based Lewis acid catalyst, *Catal. Commun.* 8 (2007) 1122–1125, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catcom.2006.10.031>.
- [41] R.A. Omer, A. Hughes, J.R. Hama, W. Wang, H. Tai, Hydrogels from dextran and soybean oil by UV photo-polymerization, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 132 (2015) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.41446>.
- [42] A. Luo, X. Jiang, H. Lin, J. Yin, “Thiol-ene” photo-cured hybrid materials based on POSS and renewable vegetable oil, *J. Mater. Chem.* 21 (2011) 12753–12760, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c1jm11425e>.
- [43] D. Kim, S. Kim, S. Jeong, M. Kim, W.K. Hong, H.B. Jeon, H.Y. Cho, S.M. Noh, H. jong Paik, Thermally latent vinyl crosslinking of polymers via sulfoxide chemistry, *Eur. Polym. J.* 179 (2022) 111520. DOI: 10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2022.111520.
- [44] R.A. Andersons, R. Grūbe, L. Vevere, P. Cabulis, M. Kirpluks, Anisotropic thermal expansion of bio-based rigid low-density closed-cell polyurethane foams, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 16 (2022) 1517–1525, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2021.12.094>.
- [45] I. Bute, S. Tarasovs, S. Vidinejevs, L. Vevere, J. Sevcenko, A. Aniskevich, Thermal properties of 3D printed products from the most common polymers, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 124 (2023) 2739–2753, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-022-10657-7>.
- [46] S. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, ISO 8301 1991, Thermal insulation — Determination of steady-state thermal resistance and related properties Heat flow meter apparatus, (1991).
- [47] S. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, ISO 4590:2016, Rigid cellular plastics — Determination of the volume percentage of open cells and of closed cells, (2016).
- [48] ISO 844:2021; Rigid cellular plastics — Determination of compression properties, International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland, 2021.
- [49] R. Pomilovskis, I. Mierina, A. Fridrihsone, M. Kirpluks, Bio-based polymer developments from tall oil fatty acids by exploiting Michael addition, *Polymers (Basel)* 14 (2022) 4068, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14194068>.
- [50] G.F. Levchik, K. Si, S.V. Levchik, G. Camino, C.A. Wilkie, Correlation between cross-linking and thermal stability: cross-linked polystyrenes and polymethacrylates, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 65 (1999) 395–403, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(99\)00028-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(99)00028-2).
- [51] J. Liao, Y. Hou, J. Li, M. Zhang, Y. Dong, X. Chen, Lightweight and recyclable hybrid multifunctional foam based cellulose fibers with excellent flame retardant, thermal, and acoustic insulation property, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 244 (2023) 110315, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110315>.
- [52] R.K. Pal, P. Goyal, S. Sehgal, Effect of cellulose fibre based insulation on thermal performance of buildings, *Mater. Today Proc.* 45 (2021) 5778–5781, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.02.749>.
- [53] A.A. Septevani, D.A.C. Evans, P.K. Annamalai, D.J. Martin, The use of cellulose nanocrystals to enhance the thermal insulation properties and sustainability of rigid polyurethane foam, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 107 (2017) 114–121, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.05.039>.
- [54] K.T. Yucel, C. Basyigit, C. Ozel, Thermal insulation properties of expanded polystyrene as construction and insulating materials, 15th symp Thermophys. Prop. (2003) 54–66.
- [55] A. Abbad, K. Jaboviste, M. Ouisse, N. Dauchez, Acoustic performances of silicone foams for sound absorption, *J. Cell. Plast.* 54 (2018) 651–670, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021955X17732305>.
- [56] B.E. Obi, Overview of applications of polymeric foams, *Polym. Foam. Struct.* (2018) 3–14, <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-1-4557-7755-6.00001-x>.
- [57] A. Abolins, R. Pomilovskis, E. Vanags, I. Mierina, S. Michalowski, A. Fridrihsone, M. Kirpluks, Impact of different epoxidation approaches of tall oil fatty acids on rigid polyurethane foam thermal insulation, *Materials (Basel)* 14 (2021) 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14040894>.